

Production of biodiesel from vegetable oil and microalgae by fatty acid extraction and enzymatic esterification

Running title: Biodiesel by enzymatic esterification from microalgae

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The aim of this work was to obtain biodiesel (methyl esters) from the saponifiable lipids (SLs) fraction of the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, whose biomass dry weight contains 12.1 wt% of these lipids. SLs were extracted from the microalga as free fatty acids (FFAs) for subsequent transformation to methyl esters (biodiesel) by enzymatic esterification. Extraction as FFAs rather than as SLs allows them to be obtained with higher purity. Microalgal FFAs were obtained by direct saponification of lipids in the biomass and subsequent extraction-purification with hexane. Esterification of FFAs with methanol was catalysed by lipase Novozym 435 from *Candida antarctica*. Stability studies of this lipase in the operational conditions showed that the esterification degree (ED) attained with the same batch of lipase remained constant over six reaction cycles (36 h total reaction time). The optimal conditions attained for 4 g of FFAs were 25 °C, 200 rpm, methanol/FFA molar ratio of 1.5:1, Novozym 435/FFA ratio of 0.025:1 w/w and 4 h reaction time. In these conditions the ED attained was 92.6%, producing a biodiesel with 83 wt% purity from microalgal FFAs. Several experimental scales were tested (from 4 to 40 g FFAs), and in all cases similar EDs were obtained.

Keywords: biodiesel, microalga, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, lipase, Novozym 435, free fatty acid, used vegetable oil

Biodiesel is defined as the monoalkyl esters of long chain fatty acids from vegetable oils and animal fats, for use in ignition-compression engines (diesel). It is a renewable, biodegradable and non-toxic biofuel. The depletion of fossil fuel reserves, together with heightened awareness of climate change and contaminant emissions, have led to increased interest in biodiesel as a potential alternative to fossil fuels (1-2).

Compared to the two previous generations of biodiesel feedstocks (i.e. food and non-food crops), the third generation, microalgae, has appeared to be a suitable energy source for biodiesel production. Algae use sunlight to produce oils, but they do so more efficiently than crop plants due to their higher productivity (3). Moreover, some species can accumulate large amounts of lipids and they do not need high quality agricultural land or even high quality water to grow biomass. However, the production cost of high grade algae oils constitutes an obstacle in the short term. The main reason is that the operational conditions leading to high grade oil in microalgae are usually those providing low growth rates (low temperature, low light intensity and nitrogen deficiency) (4). Use of the biorefinery concept will help to lower the cost of production. Like a petroleum refinery, a biorefinery uses every component of the biomass raw material to produce useable products (3).

Now biodiesel is commonly produced by using basic catalysts, such as sodium or potassium hydroxides, since these catalysts give high yield in short reaction times. However, in the case of oils with high contents of free fatty acids (FFAs), such as microalgal oils, alkaline catalysis presents some problems due to the formation of soaps, which decreases the biodiesel yield and increases the purification costs. Acid catalysts transform both FFAs and acylglycerols into methyl esters (5). However, the reaction velocity of transesterification with an acid-catalyst is much slower than with an alkaline

one and more methanol is required (6). In addition, acid catalysts are highly corrosive and so are seldom used on an industrial scale.

Lipases also catalyse the transformation of both FFAs and acylglycerols to methyl esters, but at lower temperatures than in alkaline and acid catalysis (30–40 °C). Moreover, the purification of biodiesel is easier, cheaper and entails a lower consumption of water, because neither alkalis nor acids need to be separated, only the excess of alcohol and the glycerol. This glycerol is also easily recuperated at a high degree of purity (without mixing with alkalis or acids), and it can be used in nobler applications. On the other hand, if the lipase is immobilized, the separation of the reaction mixture and the catalyst is straightforward. Many works on the enzymatic production of biodiesel have studied the effect of methanol on the stability of the lipase, because when methanol exceeds the solubility limit in the reaction mixture the lipase is irreversibly deactivated. To address this problem several alternatives have been put forward, such as the addition of methanol by steps (7), the immobilization of lipase (8) and the utilization of solvents, such as tert-butanol (9).

Biodiesel production from algae can be carried out by different methods. The most common one is a two-step method in which algae oil is extracted with organic solvent and then converted to biodiesel. Also, some authors use the direct extraction-transesterification of lipids in algae, catalysed by an acid or an enzyme (10). Tran *et al.* (10) compared the transesterification of the extracted microalgal oil and the direct enzyme transesterification of oil in previously disrupted biomass. Their results show that the latter procedure achieved higher biodiesel conversion (72.1 % and 97.3 %wt oil, respectively).

The goal of this work was to produce biodiesel from microalgae by an alternative two-step enzymatic procedure: (i) extraction of purified saponifiable lipids (SLs) as

FFAs by direct saponification in the microalgal biomass, and (ii) enzymatic esterification of the extracted FFAs with methanol. Due to the difficulty of producing sufficient amounts of microalgal FFAs, the optimization experiments were carried out with FFAs from used vegetable oil and the optimal conditions were then applied to FFAs from the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana*. The findings show that similar results were attained with both FFAs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microalga, oil, lipases and chemicals Wet paste biomass of the marine microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* was used as an oil-rich substrate. This biomass was facilitated by the “Estación experimental de Las Palmerillas” (Cajamar, El Ejido, Spain). Cells were grown in an outdoor tubular photobioreactor, centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 10 min, and then stored at -20 °C until use. This wet biomass contained 24.2% ± 0.7% w/w of dry biomass and 29.1 ± 0.0 wt% of total lipids on dry biomass. The total fatty acid content (or saponifiable lipids as equivalent fatty acids) in the biomass was 12.1 ± 0.2 wt% on dry biomass. Free fatty acids (FFAs) from used vegetable oil (UVO) were also used. This oil was provided by the biodiesel manufacturer company Albabío (Níjar, Spain). Table 1 shows the fatty acid composition of both oils. The esterification reaction was catalyzed by the lipase Novozym 435 from *Candida antarctica* (Novozymes A/S, Bagsvaerd, Denmark). This lipase is immobilized on a macroporous acrylic resin and it is positionally non-specific.

Ethanol (96%, analysis quality) and hexane (95% purity, synthesis quality), both of Panreac (Barcelona, Spain), were used to extract FFAs from the microalga and to saponify the UVO. HCl (37%, Panreac S.A., Barcelona, Spain), methanol (99.9% purity, Carlo Erba Reagents, Rodano, Italy), NaOH and KOH (85% purity, J.T. Baker,

Deventer, Holland), all of analytical quality, were also used. All reagents used in the analytical determinations were also of analytical grade.

Obtaining of FFAs from UVO and microalgal biomass FFAs from UVO were obtained by saponification of the oil. The reaction mixture contained 350 mL of oil and 700 mL of a hydroalcoholic solution of NaOH, which was prepared dissolving 120 g of NaOH in 400 mL of water and 400 mL of ethanol (96% v/v). The saponification was carried out shaking this mixture at 200 rpm, at 60 °C for 30 min. The mixture was then cooled at room temperature, 140 mL of water were added and the pH was adjusted to values between 1 and 2 using 37% HCl. FFAs were extracted with 300 mL of hexane, shaking at 200 rpm for 30 min. Finally the hydroalcoholic and hexane phases were separated by decantation and the hexanic phase was washed twice with water.

FFAs from the microalga *N. gaditana* were obtained following a modification of the three-step procedure developed by Ibáñez González *et al.* (11) (Fig. 1). 0.50 kg of wet biomass was treated with 3.63 L of ethanol (96% v/v) (30 mL ethanol (96%)/g dry biomass), containing 24.2 g of KOH (85% purity) in a 10 L reactor, which was jacketed for temperature control. Direct saponification was carried out at 60 °C for 1 h with constant stirring at 200 rpm with a propeller stirrer (Eurostar digital, IKA Staufen, Germany), in argon atmosphere and covered with aluminium foil to protect from light. The biomass residue was then separated from the hydroalcoholic solution by filtration using a porous glass plate (pore diameter 100 µm, Pobel, Madrid, Spain). This biomass residue was washed with 1.4 L of ethanol (96% v/v) (14 mL ethanol (96%)/g dry biomass), to increase the fatty acid recovery yield and this washing solution was added to the hydroalcoholic fatty acid solution from the main extraction. In the following step, water (674 mL) was added to the hydroalcoholic phase to reach 30 %wt in water, to increase the immiscibility of the hydroalcoholic solution and hexane, and the

unsaponifiable contents were extracted with 4.30 L hexane (hexane/hydroalcoholic solution ratio 1:1 v/v). This extraction was carried out stirring at 200 rpm for 10 min. Subsequently, the solution was decanted for 30 min. The unsaponifiable hexanic solution was removed, leaving the lower hydroalcoholic phase in the extractor. Next, concentrated HCl was added to the hydroalcoholic phase to pH = 5, to form the FFAs. These FFAs were extracted with hexane (4.3 L), and the mixture was stirred at 200 rpm for 10 min. It was then allowed to decant for 30 min and two phases were obtained, a bottom one that was discarded and the upper hexanic phase containing the FFAs. This FFA solution was evaporated in a rotary evaporator (Buchi, R210, with vacuum pump V-700 and controller V-850, Switzerland) to remove and recover the solvent and the FFAs.

Esterification of FFAs catalysed by lipase Novozym 435 In this reaction FFAs react with methanol to produce methyl esters (biodiesel) and water in the presence of the lipase Novozym 435 which acts as catalyst. Experiments were carried out with 4 g of FFAs, 0.86 mL of methanol (methanol/FFA molar ratio 1.5:1) and different Novozym 435/FFA ratios. The esterification reaction was carried out in 50 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with silicone-capped stoppers. In a typical experiment the mixture was incubated at 40 °C and stirred in an orbital shaking air-bath (Inkubator 1000, Unimax 1010 Heidolph, Klein, Germany) at 200 rpm for 24 h. The reactions were stopped by separation of Novozym 435 by filtration. The final reaction mixture was conserved at 4 °C until analysis. Experiments were carried out modifying the following variables: reaction time, temperature, stirring velocity, methanol/FFA molar ratio and Novozym 435 amount. All reactions and their corresponding analyses were carried out in duplicate, and each value recorded is therefore the arithmetic mean of four experimental data (data shown as mean value \pm standard deviation).

Analysis of reaction products The identification of the reaction products (FFAs, methyl esters and to lesser extent acylglycerols) was carried out by thin layer chromatography (TLC), followed by gas chromatography (GC), to determine quantitatively the species present. The fatty acid profile of the oils was also determined by GC. TLC was carried out on plates of silica-gel (Precoated TLC plates, SIL G-25; Macherey-Nagel, Sigma–Aldrich), activated by heating at 105 °C for 30 min. The samples were spotted directly on the plate by adding 0.2 mL of reaction product mixture. The mobile phase used was chloroform/acetone/methanol (95:4.5:0.5 v/v/v). Spots of each lipid were visualized by spraying the plate with iodine vapour in a nitrogen steam. The position of the spot corresponding to each lipidic species is characterized by the response factor. Each lipid type was scraped from the plates and methylated according to the method of Rodriguez-Ruiz *et al.* (12). Fatty acid methyl esters were analysed by GC with an Agilent Technology 6890 gas chromatograph (Avondale, PA) using a capillary column of fused silica Omegawax™ (0.25 mm × 30 mm, 0.25 µm standard film, Supelco, Bellefonte, PA), and a FID (flame-ionization detector). Nitrogen was the carrier gas. Nonadecanoic acid (19:0) (Sigma-Aldrich) was used as internal standard for quantitative determination of fatty acids. Matreya (Pleasant Gap, PA) n-3 PUFAs (polyunsaturated fatty acids) standard (catalogue number 1177) was used for the quantitative determination of fatty acids.

The esterification degree (ED) represents the percentage of initial FFAs consumed by methylation. ED was determined by acid-base titration after checking that the results were similar to those obtained by TLC and GC, which take longer. The samples were diluted with acetone (ratio 1:1 v/v) and phenolphthalein was used as indicator. The samples from esterification of microalgal FFAs were washed with alumina, diluted with acetone (fatty acid/acetone ratio 1:20 v/v) and titrated, using thymol blue as indicator.

Previously the acidity of the initial reaction mixture had been determined under the same conditions in which the acidity was measured, once the reaction had finished. ED was calculated by the equation:

$$ED (\%) = \frac{V_0 - V}{V_0} 100 \quad (1)$$

where V_0 and V are the volumes of 1 or 0.1 N NaOH solution used in the titration of the initial mixture and esterification product, respectively. To determine the purity of the FFAs and methyl ester from the FFA microalgal extract and esterification reaction products, respectively, a sample of known weight was analyzed by GC. Purity (wt%) was determined as the ratio between the methyl ester weight obtained by GC and the sample weight.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extraction of free fatty acids (FFAs) from the microalga *N. gaditana* FFAs from the microalga *N. gaditana* were extracted by the procedure shown in Fig. 1, which is an adaptation to this microalga of a similar process applied to the microalgae *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* (11) and *Isochrysis galbana* (13). By this procedure 83.4±3.1 wt% of fatty acids contained in the microalgal biomass were recovered and these FFAs were extracted with 73.5±2.6 wt% purity. On the other hand, saponifiable lipids (SLs) without transforming in FFAs were also extracted in our laboratory by a similar two-step process: (1) extraction of lipid from the wet microalgal biomass with ethanol (96% v/v) and (2) purification of these extracted lipids by a second extraction with hexane. This method achieved a similar SL recovery yield (85%), but the SL purity was only 31%, the impurities consisting mainly of unsaponifiable lipids (carotenoids), which obviously can not be transformed into methyl esters (biodiesel). The

transformation of SLs into FFAs by direct saponification in the biomass (Fig. 1) allows easier separation of FFAs and unsaponifiable lipids, and, therefore, a higher purity of the final biodiesel. Besides, the extraction of SLs as FFAs does not imply an excessive increasing of the economical cost because only an alkali, as NaOH or KOH, have to be added to the extraction solvent (ethanol) to transform SLs to FFAs.

Influence of reaction time The experiments of optimization of the enzymatic reaction conditions were carried out with FFAs from UVO (used vegetable oil) and the best conditions were applied to FFAs extracted from the microalgal biomass. Novozym 435 was chosen to catalyse this reaction because it is one of the most widely used lipases in industry and for biodiesel production (7, 14-17). These experiments were firstly carried out at small scale (4 g of FFAs from UVO), using a 1.5:1 methanol/FFA molar ratio and a 0.1 w/w lipase/FFA ratio (40 °C and 200 rpm). In these conditions it was observed that for a reaction time of 0.5 h a 92.8% conversion was attained, and this conversion kept practically constant until 24 h (around 94.6 % at 2, 6 and 24 h). This reaction was scaled-up maintaining the same operational conditions. Fig. 2 shows that at 0.5 h the conversion is again over 90% and the equilibrium yields attained at both scales are similar (about 95%).

In the following experiment, the conditions previously applied to FFAs from UVO were applied to FFAs extracted from the microalga *N. gaditana*, although in this case 14.3 g of microalgal FFAs were used (Fig. 2). It was observed that the esterification degree (ED) exceeded 90% at 0.25 h of reaction, attaining values of over 95% at only 0.5 h, i.e. the reaction velocity and conversions were equal to or better than those obtained with FFAs from UVO.

These data (Fig. 2) show the high velocity of transformation of FFAs to methyl esters, which is much faster than the transesterification reaction velocity (acylglycerols

+ alcohol). This reaction velocity is higher than that obtained by Da Rós *et al.* (15) in the production of biodiesel from cyanobacterial lipids, also using Novozym 435; these authors attained an ethyl ester yield of 98.1% after reaction times of 48 h using iso-octane as reaction media. This result is logical because, in fact, the formation of methyl esters from SLs by transesterification occurs in a two-step process, that is, the oil is first hydrolyzed to FFAs and partial glycerides and the FFAs produced are then esterified with methanol (18). By the procedure assayed in this work the first step of hydrolysis is avoided.

Reuse of lipase As mentioned above, it is known that many lipases are deactivated in the presence of short chain alcohols, such as methanol and ethanol. This is particularly noticeable when no solvent is used, since it is the non-dissolved alcohol which deactivates the lipase (7). To test the stability of Novozym 435 in the esterification of FFAs with methanol, experiments were carried out in which the same batch of Novozym 435 was used to catalyse successive reactions. In these experiments the operational conditions shown in Fig. 2 were maintained constant and the influence of washing the biomass between reactions was also tested. The washing was carried out with an acetone/ethanol 1:1 (v/v) mixture (19). Table 2 shows the ED attained in six uses of the same batch of lipase in reactions of 2 and 6 h, both with and without washing. Table 2 shows that there was no appreciable diminution of the ED. Neither was the conversion affected by washing the lipase between the catalyzed reactions, and therefore washing is not considered necessary before reuse. These results show the stability of lipase Novozym 435 in the operational conditions required for the esterification of FFAs to produce methyl esters (biodiesel) in absence of solvent, since the ED remained constant at approximately 94% over at least six reactions catalysed by the same batch of lipase. This stability contrasts, for example, with the loss of activity

of this lipase during repeated experiments carried out by Du et al. (16) in the transesterification of soybean oil with methanol. According to these authors this activity loss might be due to the inactivation effect caused by methanol and the negative effect caused by the by-product glycerol on the surface of immobilized lipase. Therefore, this higher stability of the lipase in the esterification reaction may be due to factors such as the absence of glycerol in this reaction and the shorter reaction time of esterification compared with the transesterification times. On the other hand, Lin et al. (2) stated that a high content of FFAs could protect the whole cell of lipase-producing *Rhizopus oryzae* from denaturation. In the esterification of oleic acid with methanol, these authors found that the methanol concentration at which this lipase is inhibited increased with increasing FFA content.

Influence of the methanol/FFA molar ratio Table 3 shows the ED attained at increasing methanol/FFA molar ratios. It can be seen that the higher the molar ratio the higher the ED, since the esterification equilibrium is displaced toward the formation of products when the molar ratio increases. The highest ED was obtained with a methanol/FFA molar ratio of 2. However, the ED only improved by 1% with respect to the 1.5 molar ratio, although the amount of methanol increased 33%. Therefore a methanol/FFA molar ratio of 1.5 was chosen for future experiments. It is important to operate with a low methanol/FFA ratio, since the higher the methanol concentration is, the higher the possibility that the lipase is deactivated, especially when no solvent is used (7). However, some authors use high molar ratios to increase the conversion. For instance, Da Rós *et al.* (15) use an ethanol/lipids molar ratio of 12:1 (equivalent to 4:1 alcohol/FFA), in the transesterification of the lipids from the cyanobacterium *Microcystis aeruginosa*, catalysed by Novozym 435, although these authors used tert-butanol or iso-octane to preserve the stability of the lipase. On the other hand, the low methanol/FFA

ratio used in this work contrasts with the high ratios that are required for the production of biodiesel by esterification of FFAs by acid catalysis. Su (20) established an optimal methanol/FFA molar ratio of 10:1 in the esterification of FFAs from soybean oil catalysed by hydrochloric acid, and Hayyan *et al.* (21) used a methanol/oil molar ratio of 8:1 (about 2.7:1 as equivalent FFAs) in the transesterification-esterification of sludge palm oil with 23 wt% FFAs.

Influence of temperature and intensity of treatment (IOT) Table 4 shows the ED attained at three temperatures and several IOTs. The IOT is the Novozym 435 amount \times reaction time / FFA amount, and the reaction velocity is proportional to this variable if no enzyme deactivation occurs (22).

The temperatures at which Novozym 435 is most frequently used are 30 °C (7, 17) and 40 °C (14, 16), and therefore both temperatures were tested in the present work. In addition, 25 °C was assayed in an attempt to reduce the reaction temperature and increase the lipase stability. Table 4 shows that the EDs obtained at 25 °C (between 92 and 93%) were similar to those obtained at 30 and 40 °C for the esterification of FFAs with methanol in the experimental conditions shown in this table 4. Consequently the lowest temperature, 25 °C, was chosen.

The IOT was modified between 0.05 and 0.5 g Novozym 435 \times h/g FFAs and in this range there was no important influence on the methyl ester yield, which suggests that the equilibrium was attained at these IOTs. Therefore an IOT = 0.1 g Novozym 435 \times h/g FFAs was chosen. This IOT can be attained, for example, with a reaction time of 4 h and 0.1 g Novozym 435, for 4 g FFAs (i.e. 2.5 wt% of Novozym 435 with respect to FFAs), although the reaction time can be reduced using a larger amount of lipase. In the transesterification of oils to produce biodiesel, the Novozym 435 amount is often 4 wt% (7, 16) or 10 wt% of Novozym 435 (14) with respect to oil and reaction times in the

range of 24–72 h. Therefore, IOTs of around 2–3 g Novozym 435×h/g oil are used depending on the oil treated (7,14,16). However, IOTs for the esterification reaction must be at least 20 times lower than for the transesterification reaction, which is logically due to the higher reaction velocity of the esterification reaction. Véras *et al.* (23) clearly demonstrate this fact in the production of fatty acid ethyl esters by simultaneous esterification and transesterification, catalysed by Novozym 435, of highly acidic feedstock; the first order velocity constants for the esterification and transesterification reactions were in the ranges 0.92–1.20 h⁻¹ and 0.11–0.13 h⁻¹, respectively. The conversion of the FFA fraction to fatty acid ethyl esters was about 90% at a reaction time of 4 h with 1.5% w/v of Novozym 435, i.e. an IOT of around 0.067 g×h/g, which is similar to that obtained in this work.

Influence of the addition of molecular sieves and stirring velocity Novozym 435 has been shown to contain enough water in its support medium to preserve its catalytic activity in an anhydrous medium (24). However, water is produced in the esterification reaction, and if it is not necessary to preserve the lipase activity, it could be removed from the reaction medium to displace the reaction equilibrium toward the formation of methyl esters. Esteban Cerdán *et al.* (25) demonstrated the importance of removing the water produced to increase the conversion of the esterification of glycerol and polyunsaturated fatty acids; in that work water was removed by the addition of molecular sieves. However, Table 3 shows that in this case the addition of molecular sieves of 3 and 4 Å did not increase the methyl ester yields obtained at low and high reaction times. Experiments were also carried out at 25 °C with similar results. Also Haas and Scott (26) failed to increase the conversion of the enzymatic esterification of FFAs to biodiesel (in the production of biodiesel from soapstocks, by enzymatic catalysis) by using molecular sieves, what was attributed to the high viscosity of the

reaction mixture. At this respect, other authors (9,27) did succeed in increasing the conversion of the esterification using molecular sieves, but in these cases tert-butanol was used as reaction medium, what decreases the viscosity and can speed up transfer of water towards the molecular sieves. On the other hand, Lee et al. (5) added molecular sieves to adsorb methanol, which decreases its concentration in the reaction medium and avoids deactivation of the lipase. However, this addition would remove one of the reactants and would reduce the reaction rate. These results indicate that the role of the molecular sieves in the reaction medium is complex and a detailed study is required.

With regard to the stirring rate ED of 60.9 ± 2.0 , 89.4 ± 1.2 , 92.3 ± 0.6 , 93.2 ± 0.2 , and 94.4 ± 0.0 % were obtained, respectively, without stirring and at 100, 200, 300 and 400 rpm (using a methanol/FFA molar ratio 1.5:1, IOT = 0.1 and 25 °C), i.e. when the stirring velocity increases, so does the ED, which indicates that, at less until 100 rpm the mass transfer influences the reaction velocity. However, from 200 rpm the ED increases by only 2% when the stirring velocity is doubled, which may indicate that beyond 200 rpm the reaction is kinetically controlled. As a result, 200 rpm appears to be an adequate stirring velocity at this scale and this fact should be taken into account at large scale.

Esterification of the microalgal FFAs in the optimal conditions The optimal conditions for the esterification of FFAs from UVO were: 25 °C, 1.5:1 methanol/FFA molar ratio, stirring at 200 rpm, IOT = 0.1 g Novozym 435/h/g FFAs (for example 0.1 g Novozym 435 and 4 h for 4 g of FFAs) and absence of molecular sieves. The reaction velocity can be increased and the reaction time reduced using higher lipase amounts. These conditions were used for the esterification of FFAs from the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana*. The ED attained was $92.6 \pm 0.5\%$, similar to that obtained with FFAs from UVO in these conditions (92.3%). This yield is similar to those

obtained by other authors who transform FFAs into biodiesel using other catalysts. For example Hayyan *et al.* (21) reduced the FFA content of sludge palm oil by sulphuric acid catalysed esterification. This FFA content was reduced from 23.2% to less than 2% (conversion of around 91.4%) using 0.75 wt% sulphuric acid, an 8:1 molar ratio of methanol to oil (2.7:1 expressed as methanol/FFA, as opposed to 1.5:1 in the present work), 60 °C (25 °C in this work) and 60 min for a similar conversion to that attained in this work. This comparison shows that enzymatic catalysis consumes less energy than acid catalysis and can even give higher reaction velocities if higher lipase amounts are used. Krohn *et al.* (28) produced algal biodiesel from oils with high FFA content from several microalgae species using supercritical methanol and porous titania microspheres in a fixed bed reactor to catalyse the simultaneous conversion of triacylglycerols and FFAs to biodiesel; a maximum conversion of 85% was attained and this method requires very high pressures (2250 psi) and temperatures (340 °C).

The microalgal biodiesel obtained from the esterification reaction was 78.6 ± 1.3 wt% pure, which is similar to the purity of FFAs extracted from microalgal biomass (73.5 ± 2.6 wt%) following the procedure shown in Fig. 1. This result highlights the fact that the enzymatic conversion of FFAs to methyl esters does not reduce biodiesel purity.

Conclusions This work studied the enzymatic production of biodiesel by esterification of FFAs from UVO and the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana*. Saponifiable lipids (SLs) were first extracted from microalgal biomass as FFAs, which allows them to be obtained with a high degree of purity (73.5 wt%), because microalgal FFAs are easier to purify than microalgal SLs. Novozym 435 from *Candida antarctica* was chosen to catalyse this esterification due its high activity (or ED attained) and its high stability in the reaction conditions. Although no solvent was used, the ED obtained in six reactions (of 2 and 6 h each), catalysed with the same batch of lipase, remained

constant. The optimal conditions for the esterification of FFAs with methanol were established with FFAs from UVO and the maximum ED attained was reproduced with FFAs from the microalga *N. gaditana* (92.6 %). These optimal conditions are: 1.5:1 methanol/FFA molar ratio, 25 °C, stirring at 200 rpm (with 4 g of FFAs), IOT = 0.1 g Novozym 435 ×h/g FFAs (for example 0.1 g Novozym 435 and 4 h for 4 g of FFAs). This IOT is much lower than that required to produce biodiesel from microalgal lipids, because the esterification of FFAs occurs much faster than the transesterification of SLs. Moreover, the biodiesel obtained from FFAs is purer (78.6 wt%) than that obtained from lipids. The enzymatic catalysis of the esterification of FFAs to produce biodiesel also consumes less methanol and energy than acid catalysis.

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Figure legends

FIG. 1. Process to extract and purify fatty acids from the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana*.

FIG. 2. Influence of reaction time on the esterification degree (ED) of free fatty acids (FFAs) from used vegetable oil (UVO) (closed circles) and the microalgal biomass from *N. gaditana* (open squares) catalysed by Novozym 435 at large scale (scaling factor 10 and 3.6). Operational conditions for FFAs from UVO: 40 g FFAs, 8.6 mL methanol (methanol/FFA molar ratio 1.5:1), 4 g Novozym 435 (Novozym 435/FFA ratio 0.1:1 w/w), 200 rpm and 40 °C. For FFAs from microalgal biomass: 14.3 g FFAs, 3.08 mL methanol (molar ratio methanol/FFA 1.5:1), 1.43 g Novozym 435 (Novozym 435/FFA ratio 0.1:1 w/w), 200 rpm and 40 °C.

TABLE 1. Fatty acids composition (percentage with respect to the total fatty acids of biomass) of the wet paste biomass from *Nannochloropsis gaditana* and from the used vegetable oil (UVO).

Fatty acid	Microalgal oil (wt %)	UVO (wt %)
14:0	6.0 ± 0.1	-
16:0	23.8 ± 0.0	9.1 ± 0.1
16:1n7	22.2 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.0
18:0	0.5 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.0
18:1n9	5.9 ± 0.1	49.5 ± 0.3
18:1n7	-	0.9 ± 0.0
18:2n6	4.8 ± 0.0	34.6 ± 0.4
20:4n6	6.9 ± 0.2	-
20:5n3	27.5 ± 0.5	0.6 ± 0.0
Others	2.5 ± 0.4	0.9 ± 0.0

TABLE 2. Influence of the number of uses of a batch of lipase Novozym 435 on the esterification degree (ED) attained in the esterification of free fatty acids (FFAs) with methanol.

Reaction time (h)	Cycle	Washing of lipase	No washing of lipase
2	1	94.0 ± 0.1	94.0 ± 0.1
	2	95.0 ± 0.1	94.9 ± 0.1
	3	94.1 ± 0.7	94.0 ± 0.9
	4	94.3 ± 0.1	94.2 ± 0.2
	5	94.7 ± 0.1	94.7 ± 0.1
	6	94.4 ± 0.1	94.7 ± 0.1
6	1	95.1 ± 0.2	95.1 ± 0.2
	2	95.5 ± 0.0	95.2 ± 0.0
	3	94.6 ± 0.6	94.1 ± 0.3
	4	94.6 ± 0.0	94.2 ± 0.0
	5	94.8 ± 0.0	94.9 ± 0.1
	6	94.2 ± 0.0	94.3 ± 0.1

Experiments were carried out washing the lipase with an acetone/ethanol 1:1 v/v mixture and without washing, over six reaction cycles and with reaction times of 2 and 6 h. *Operational conditions:* 4 g FFAs from UVO, 0.86 mL methanol (methanol/FFA molar ratio 1.5:1), 0.4 g Novozym 435, 40 °C, 200 rpm, reaction times of 2 and 6 h.

TABLE 3. (A) Influence of the methanol/FFA molar ratio and (B) influence of the addition of 3 and 4 Å molecular sieves on the ED.

(A) Methanol/FFA molar ratio	ED (%)
0.85	86.6 ± 0.1
1.0	90.1 ± 0.1
1.2	92.8 ± 0.3
1.5	94.0 ± 0.1
2.0	95.0 ± 0.1
(B) Molecular sieves	ED (%)
No	92.8 ± 0.6
4Å	91.2 ± 0.2
3Å	91.5 ± 0.3

Operational conditions: (A) 4 g FFAs from UVO, 0.4 g Novozym 435, 200 rpm, 2 h and 40 °C. (B) 4 g FFAs from UVO, 0.86 mL methanol (methanol/FFA molar ratio 1.5), 0.4 g Novozym 435, 0.5 h, 40 °C, 200 rpm and 1.28 g molecular sieves.

TABLE 4. Influence of temperature and intensity of treatment (IOT = Novozym 435 amount \times reaction time/FFA amount) on the ED.

T (°C)	t (h)	Novozym 435 amount (g)	IOT (g Novozym 435 \times h/g FFAs)	ED (%)
25	3	0.13	0.10	92.4 \pm 0.1
	4	0.10	0.10	92.3 \pm 0.6
	4	0.20	0.20	92.8 \pm 0.1
	6	0.33	0.50	93.0 \pm 0.2
30	3	0.13	0.10	92.8 \pm 0.1
	2	0.40	0.20	93.6 \pm 0.1
	4	0.25	0.25	94.1 \pm 0.1
40	2	0.10	0.05	92.2 \pm 0.3
	2	0.20	0.10	94.0 \pm 0.1
	4	0.10	0.20	92.1 \pm 0.3

Operational conditions: 4 g FFAs from UVO, 0.86 mL of methanol (methanol/FFA molar ratio 1.5:1) and 200 rpm.